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**Taxonomy and molecular systematic position of freshwater genus
Racekiela (Porifera: Spongillida) with the description of a new species
from Northwest Mexico**

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Abstract

Racekiela montemflumina sp. nov. is the first species of the genus *Racekiela* found in freshwater habitats from Mexico. The species is abundant in small creeks at the northern side of the Durango State, located between 2500 and 2700 m altitude. The description of the new species is provided together with “*in situ*” photographs of specimens, and SEM photographs of the spicules and gemmular structure. Two distinct classes of gemmuloscleres differing in size and shape (birotules and pseudobirotules) are present. The rotule of the birotula is discoidal, flat or slightly umbonate, with serrated margins and small crenulate teeth, or spines. The proportion of rotule diameter vs. length of the shaft is the lowest of all the *Racekiela* species. Rotule of pseudobirotule is small, umbonate or with a prominent spike, and with hooks curved toward the shaft or almost straight. The birotules are embedded in the theca, but pseudobirotules protrude from the outer gemmular membrane. Fragments of cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI) mtDNA, and internal transcribed spacers 1 and 2 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2) rDNA were sequenced in order to establish

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3 the molecular identity and systematic position of genus *Racekiela* and the new species. COI
4 showed an identical nucleotide composition with at least 11 spongillid-specimens from 6
5 species previously sequenced (Genbank). Phylogenetic analysis using the ribosomal region
6 was according with previous approximations for freshwater sponges, showing the
7 monophyly of family Lubomirskiidae, and the non-monophyly of families Spongillidae and
8 Malawispongiidae. Owing to the genera were clustered in not monophyletic separate
9 clades. Specifically, *Racekiela montemflumina* sp. nov. erected as a sister clade of several
10 species from the genera *Ephydatia* and *Cortispongilla*. Our species constitutes the first
11 representative of genus *Racekiela* sequenced. This is also the first record of a freshwater
12 sponge in Mexico since decades ago.
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23 **Key Words:** *Racekiela*, Barcoding, COI, ITS, Spongillidae, Freshwater sponge.
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27 **Introduction**

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32 Freshwater sponges are members of the Porifera that successfully colonized a wide
33 variety of lentic and lotic habitats such as springs, streams, rapids, falls, swamps, rivers,
34 estuaries, lakes, thermal vents and springs, caldera lakes, tectonic lakes, alpine lakes,
35 ancient lakes, salt lakes, karstic caves, anchialine caves, ephemeral water bodies in both
36 temperate and strictly arid climates (Manconi & Pronzato 2008).
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40 Based on their morphology they were included into Order Haplosclerida suborder
41 Spongillina, which comprising seven families (Manconi & Pronzato, 2002), but according
42 to molecular data (Borchiellini et al., 2004) freshwater sponges are not true Haplosclerida,
43 and recently, the suborder was upgraded to order rank (Morrow & Cárdenas, 2015).
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48 Systematics and distribution of freshwater sponges in Mexico is still poorly known. This
49 is due to the scarcity of records and that there are still many unexplored and/or poorly
50 sampled areas. To date, to our knowledge only 14 publications have recorded the presence
51 of these sponges in Mexico: Potts (1885a/1887); Old (1936); Martínez (1940); Rioja
52 (1940a, 1940b, 1940c/1942/1953a, 1953b); Penney & Racek (1968); Bushnell (1971); Frost
53 (1991); Manconi & Pronzato (2005). The number of species reported in the cited references
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3 are 12, however, it's necessary to re-study the specimens cited in the oldest literature to
4 revise their ascription to the various species, and by the moment we need to consider this
5 number with caution.
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9 The species described here belong to *Racekiela*, a genus proposed by Bass & Volkmer-
10 Ribeiro (1998) to replace genus *Acanthodiscus* because it was preoccupied by a mollusk
11 (Volkmer-Ribeiro, 1996, Manconi & Pronzato, 2002). *Racekiela* is characterized by having
12 two classes of gemmuloscleres; birotules with short shaft and pseudobirotules with long
13 and spined shaft; and absence of microscleres (Manconi & Pronzato, 2002). This last
14 characteristic differentiates *Racekiela* from the genus *Heteromeyenia* Potts (1881). The
15 close genus, *Anheteromeyenia* Schröder (1927), is also clearly different because has not
16 microscleres and has only one category of gemmuloscleres (pseudobirotules).
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19 The aims of this paper were to describe a new species of *Racekiela*, the first of the genus
20 from Mexico, and to establish the molecular systematic position of the genus among the
21 freshwater sponges, corroborating if this is inserted into the principal Spongillidae clade as
22 morphology has suggested.
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25 26 27 28 29 30 31 **Materials and Methods**

32 33 34 **Sampling localities and collecting**

35 Sponges were visually located in the peripheral shallow margins of three creeks of the
36 Durango State (Northwest Mexico). The creeks were located in the ecotourism complex of
37 Mexiquillo (23°42'58.34"N -105°38'48.79"W, 2596 m altitude), La Pirámide
38 (23°42'55.72"N - 105°29'54.31"W; 2716 m altitude), and Coscomate (23°41'59.09"N -
39 105°34'3.37"W; 2447 m altitude) (Fig. 1). Samples were preserved in ethanol (96%), and
40 all the material collected has been deposited in the Colección de Esponjas del Laboratorio
41 de Ecología del Bentos, del Instituto de Ciencias del Mar y Limnología de la Universidad
42 Nacional Autónoma de México (LEB-ICML-UNAM).
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49 50 **Skeletal**

51 To study spicular elements, a small piece of sponge was cut and placed into glass test tubes.
52 The same procedure was undertaken for studying gemmule spicules. Nitric acid was
53 dispensed into each one and the sample was boiled until the fragment is dissolved. After 1
54 hour, the nitric acid was pipetted out of the tube and distilled water was added. The sample
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3 was left to settle for 10 minutes, and this was repeated two times to ensure all the nitric acid
4 was removed. Finally, pure ethanol was added to each sample. For Light Microscopy (LM),
5 permanent preparations were made of body “tissue”, as well as gemmule-spicules taking a
6 small drop of ethanol containing the spicules, which were placed onto a slide and heated
7 until all liquid evaporated. Once the sample was dry a drop of mounting resin of Canada
8 balsam was added and the coverslip was applied. The slide was then placed under a
9 microscope and 25 measurements of each type of spicules (length /width shaft, and rotule
10 diameter) were made using a calibrated micrometer (LM). For Scanning Electron
11 Microscopy (SEM), spicules isolated with above method were mounted on the SEM stub
12 with the help of double sided carbon-tape. Samples were sputter-coated with gold and
13 scanned and photographed using Analytical SEM (JEOL).
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24 **Molecular analyses: DNA purification, amplification and sequencing**

25 Total genomic DNA was isolated from three individuals, following the steps used by Cruz-
26 Barraza, Vega, Ávila, & Vázquez-Maldonado (2017). We amplified the mtDNA COI
27 ‘*barcoding*’ fragment from the holotype and the ribosomal rDNA encompassing the ITS1-
28 5.8S-ITS2 gene region as well for the holotype and two paratypes. The mtDNA gene was
29 amplified using universal invertebrates Folmer fragment, but with the forward primer
30 modified by Cruz-Barraza, Vega, & Carballo (2014) PLAKLCOdegF: 5'-TCW ACD AAY
31 CAT AAA GAY ATW GG-3'; and the reverse modified by Meyer, Geller, & Paulay (2005)
32 dgHCO2198 (TAA ACT TCA GGG TGA CCA AAR AAY CA-3'. The rDNA gene region
33 was amplified using primers from Wörheide (1998) RA2: GTC CCT GCC CTT TGT ACA
34 CA and ITS2.2: CCT GGT TAG TTT CTT TTC CTC CGC. PCR reactions were carried
35 out in a volume of 12.5 µl and consisted of 6.0 µl distilled H₂O (sterile MilliQ), 0.75 µl
36 dexoyribonucleotide triphosphates (0.2 mM), 0.75 µl MgCl₂ (8 mM), 0.70 µl of each
37 primer (10 µM), 2.50 µl 5x PCR buffer (Promega), 0.2 µl Taq DNA polymerase, and 1 µl
38 genomic DNA (c. 50– 100 ng). Thermal cycling conditions were: initial denaturation at
39 94°C for 2 min, and 35 cycles of 94°C for 30 s, 50°C for 30 s, 72°C for 1 min, and a final
40 extension of 72°C for 5 min. PCR-products were run in a 1.5% agarose gel to corroborate
41 the positive amplification. Products were purified using the Wizard purification kit
42 (Promega) and sequenced in both directions using Applied Biosystems 3730xl DNA
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3 analysers by Macrogen, Korea. Sequences of *Racekiela montemflumina* sp. nov., will be
4 sent to GenkBank once the manuscript is accepted.
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8 **Molecular analyses: Sequence alignment and phylogenetic reconstructions**

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10 Sequences were assembled, verified and edited with Codon Code Aligner 5.0.2
11 (CodonCode Corporation). BLAST (Search National Center for Biotechnology
12 Information/Blast) searches were used to verify the identity of sequences and check for
13 possible contamination. Available sequences of ribosomal region (ITS1 5.8S ITS2), of
14 freshwater sponges were obtained from GenBank and aligned in mega 7. (Kumar, Stecher,
15 & Tamura, 2016), using the CLUSTALW alignment under the default gap opening–gap
16 extension parameters (15.0–6.66). Alignment was edited in AliView v. 1.17 (Larsson,
17 2014) by excluded the duplicate sequences from the analyses. Finally the program Gblocks
18 0.91b (Castresana, 2000) was used to determine and exclude ambiguously aligned rDNA
19 region, under following parameters: minimum number of sequences for a conserved
20 position: 14; minimum number of sequences for a flanking position: 22; maximum number
21 of contiguous non-conserved positions: 8; minimum length of a block: 10; allowed gap
22 positions: with half; use similarity matrices: yes.
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34 Phylogenetic trees were reconstructed under Bayesian Inference (BI) and Maximum
35 Likelihood (ML) criteria, using the species of *Trochospongilla latouchiana* (EF151955) as
36 outgroup, which according to previous studies appeared basal among freshwater taxa (see
37 Addis & Peterson, 2005; Itskovich et al., 2007; Meixner et al., 2007; Redmond et al.,
38 2007). BI analyses were performed with MrBayes 3.2.1 (Ronquist & Huelsenbeck, 2003)
39 using the Hasegawa-Kishino-Yano plus Invariant sites plus Gamma distributed model of
40 sequence evolution (HKY+I+G), which was obtained through the JModelTest 2.0.7
41 program (Darriba, Taboada, Doallo, & Posada, 2012). The program was run with four
42 Markov chains, each 10 000 000 generations long. These were sampled every 100 trees
43 with a burn-in of 2500. ML analysis was generated with RAxML 8.1.11 (Stamatakis, 2014)
44 on the CIPRES science gateway v.3.3 (www.phylo.org) portal (Miller, Pfeiffer, &
45 Schwartz, 2010), using the GTRGAMMA model.
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Results

Taxonomic account

Order Spongillida Manconi & Pronzato, 2002

Family Spongillidae Gray, 1867

Genus *Racekiela* Bass & Volkmer-Ribeiro, 1998

Synonymy

[*Acanthodiscus*] Volkmer-Ribeiro, 1996: 35 [preocc.]. *Racekiela* Bass & Volkmer-Ribeiro, 1998: 125. Manconi & Pronzato 2002: 953

Type species

Heteromeyenia ryderi Potts, 1882: 13 (by subsequent designation; Volkmer-Ribeiro, 1996).

Diagnosis

Spongillidae with body shape encrusting to lobate, ramose or massive. Ectosomal skeleton with tangential megascleres on the dermal membrane and irregularly scattered erect megascleres. Choanosomal skeleton consists of irregular paucispicular isotropic network with sparse spongin. Megascleres are acanthoxeas. Microscleres absent. Gemmular theca tri-layered with gemmuloscleres radially embedded. Gemmuloscleres of two types: birotules and pseudobirotules (Manconi & Pronzato, 2002).

Racekiela montemflumina sp. nov.

Etymology. The species name refers to the ecological habitat typical of the species, always found in mountain rivers at high altitude, from the Latin *montem* (mountain) and *flumina* (river).

Examined Material

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3 **Holotype.** LEB-ICML-UNAM-4000; Mexiquillo (Pueblo Nuevo, Durango),
4 23°42'58.34"N -105°38'48.79"W; 0.3 m depth; May 03, 2015. Specimen adhered to a flat
5 rock.
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10 **Paratypes.** LEB-ICML-UNAM-4001; Mexiquillo (Pueblo Nuevo, Durango),
11 23°42'58.34"N -105°38'48.79"W; 0.4 m depth; August 23, 2016. Specimen adhered to a
12 small rock. LEB-ICML-UNAM-4002; La Pirámide (Pueblo Nuevo, Durango),
13 23°42'55.72"N - 105°29'54.31"W; 0.6 m depth; August 24, 2016. Specimen adhered to a
14 submerged tree branch.
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21 **Ecology.** It has been always found in permanent shallow running waters (less than 1 m
22 depth) located between 2400 and 2700 m in altitude, adhered mainly to rocks (Figs 2.2, 2.3,
23 2.4), sometimes on wood (Figs 3.2, 3.3, 3.4), or even directly on un-consolidate sediment
24 on the river margins. The water temperature along the year ranged from 7.6 to 18.1°C.
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28 The air average annual temperature in the study area is 17°C. The highest average
29 temperature is 31°C, occurs in the months of May and June, and the lowest, around 1.7° C,
30 in the month of January. The rains occur in summer, mainly in the months of July and
31 August, and the average annual rainfall is 550 mm
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37 **General morphology.** Encrusting and cushion-shaped sponge, with surface from irregular
38 to loose, even lobose and ramose shaped in some specimens, ranging from 5 to 60 cm in
39 diameter, and from 0.5 to 3 cm in thickness (Figs. 2, 3). Surface hispid, with numerous and
40 conspicuous oscules up to 0.9 mm in diameter. The colour alive is green when found in
41 areas exposed to sunlight, or white under stone. The green colour is due to symbiosis with
42 green algae, which is a common association within freshwater sponges. The consistency
43 alive is soft and very fragile. All the sponges collected had gemmules, whitish to yellowish
44 in colour, which were lightly visible at naked eye (Figs. 2, 3).
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51 Choanosomal skeleton is an irregular network of oxeas, with paucispicular primary
52 fibers and undefined secondary tracts. Ectosomal skeleton not observed.
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3 **Spicules.** Megascleres: Oxeas, barely microspined, straight or slightly bent (Figs 4.1, 6.1),
4 displaying an extraordinary array of malformations (Figs 4.3, 6.4). Rarely transformed to
5 styles (Fig. 4.2). Measurements: 200–325 x 7–18 μm .
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9 Gemmuloscleres are of two types. Birotules with straight shaft smooth or with 1–6 erect
10 pointed spines frequently located in the middle, which are ornamented by microspines (Figs
11 5.1, 6.3). Rotules are large, discoidal, flat or slightly umbonate; characteristically with
12 serrated margins and small crenulate teeth spines or tubercles. Sometimes with three
13 rotules (Figs 5.1, 5.2). Measurements: 47–60 x 5–13 μm ; rotule diameter 17–23 μm .
14 Pseudobirotules are longer than the former, with straight and thin shafts, which are
15 regularly spined. Rotules small, umbonate or with a prominent spike, with an irregular
16 number of hooks curved towards the shaft or almost straight, sometimes bifurcated (Figs
17 5.3, 6.2). Measurements: 87–105 x 7–13 μm .
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26 **Gemmules.** Gemmules are spherical to subspherical (Fig. 7), abundant at basal portion and
27 also scattered in the sponge body. Gemmular theca is tri-layered: the outer gemmular
28 membrane is granular (Fig. 7.5), and covers the outer rotules of the short gemmuloscleres;
29 the intermedia pneumatic layer is well-developed and composed of irregular spongin
30 chambers; the inner layer of compact spongin is sublayered with a variable number of
31 layers (Figs 7.5, 7.7, 7.8). Birotules are radially embedded in the pneumatic layer (Fig. 7.4)
32 but pseudobirotules protruding conspicuously from the outer gemmular membrane (Figs
33 7.3, 7.7). Gemmules contain a dense mass of totipotent cells (thesocytes) (Fig. 7.4).
34 Foramen simple without a discernible tube but slightly elevated (Figs 7.4, 7.6).
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44 **Molecular analyses.** All sequences were analyzed by BLAST (NCBI/Blast), confirming
45 that correspond to Spongillida (Porifera). The mitochondrial *cox1* fragment provided 659
46 pb (after clipping the sequence primers). From Blast Search, this sequence was identical to
47 11 sequences of 6 species included in GenBank: *Ephydatia muelleri* (GQ411062,
48 DQ176778, EU237481, LT158504), *Baikalospongia intermedia* (KU324767, EU000567,
49 JQ302310), *Baikalospongia bacillifera* (KJ192328), *Baikalospongia fungiformis*
50 (KF835264), *Rezinkovia echinata* (JQ302309), and *Lubomirskia baikalensis* (GU385217).
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3 The ribosomal region analyzed from the three samples of *Racekiela montemflumina* sp.
4 nov. showed identical sequences; which confirms that they belong to the same species. The
5 ITS1 gene fragment provided 252 pb while the ITS2 provided 263 pb. Blast search
6 comparison showed that our new species only differs 9% from the nearest sequence that
7 correspond to *Ephydatia* sp. 1 (AM950184) from Russia. But it is also very near to other
8 *Ephydatia*-species. We aligned sequences of ITS1-5.8-ITS2 rDNA region from 50
9 freshwater sponges including the new species. After exclude ambiguously aligned regions,
10 577 pb were available for phylogenetic analyses. The alignment revealed a total of 402
11 variable sites, 319 of which were parsimony-informative.
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20 The phylogenetic tree obtained from both analyses BI and ML, was congruent enough,
21 with small differences in relation to low supported or not resolved branches. Tree topology
22 (Fig. 8) was also congruent with previous molecular analyses (ITS's rDNA) of freshwater
23 sponges, grouped in a well-supported monophyletic clade (100PP/93BP) all members of
24 the family Lubomirskiidae (endemic of Baikal Lake). This clade formed a sister group as
25 part of family Spongillidae (*Ephydatia*, *Heterorotula*, and *Racekiela*) and
26 Malawispongiidae (*Cortispongilla*). Specifically, *Racekiela montemflumina* sp. nov. was
27 clustered as a sister clade of several species of *Ephydatia* and *Cortispongilla*. The
28 monophyly of all other Spongillidae representatives was not resolved. The genus *Spongilla*
29 was clustered as a sister group of a large clade formed by families Lubomirskiidae,
30 Spongillidae (in part), and Malawispongiidae. While the genera *Radiospongilla* and
31 *Eunapius* yielded robust monophyletic clades, although they were included in an
32 unresolved basal polytomy. The family Potamolepidae with the representative species
33 *Echinospongilla brichardi*, was included near to *Trochospongilla latouchiana* (out group)
34 (Fig. 8).
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Discussion

The main diagnostic traits to identify freshwater sponges are skeletal architecture, size and shape of spicules, and gemmular traits such as gemmular cage, gemmular theca, gemmular foramen, arrangement of spicules, shape, and ornamentations of spicules (Manconi & Pronzato 2008). These characters are notably diversified and they are diagnostic at the genus and species level. Particularly, the genus *Racekiela* is specifically characterized by having a gemmular theca tri-layered with gemmuloscleres radially embedded, which are of two types: birotules and pseudobirotules (Manconi & Pronzato, 2002). Currently, only five species of *Racekiela* are known so far: *Racekiela ryderii* (Potts, 1882 described as *Heteromeyenia ryderii*), *R. pictouensis* (Potts, 1885b as *H. pictouensis*), *R. biceps* (Lindenschmidt, 1950 as *H. biceps*), the three distributed in North America, and *R. sheilae* (Volkmer-Ribeiro, Barbosa, & Tavares, 1988 as *Anheteromeyenia sheilae*), and *R. cavernicola* (Volkmer-Ribeiro, Bichuette, & De Sousa Machado, 2010) distributed in South America (Brazil).

R. montemflumina sp. nov. differs from all these species by a set of clearly discernible characteristics, mainly related with the shape and the ornamentations of their gemmuloscleres. The closest species is *Racekiela ryderii* but *R. montemflumina* sp. nov. has longer birotules with narrower rotules than *R. ryderii*, whose rotules have a diameter similar to the length of the shaft. In fact, the proportion of the rotule diameter vs. length of the shaft in *R. montemflumina* sp. nov is the lowest of all the *Racekiela* species (Table 1). Pseudobirotules are also quite different in the two species. Those of *R. montemflumina* are longest, having small spines distributed more uniformly along the shaft. While those of *R. ryderii* are shorter and with sparsely distributed spines along the shaft (see SEM images in Manconi & Pronzato, 2002 p. 955). The others two North American *Racekiela* are also quite different to the new species regarding to the birotules and pseudobitorules size and morphology (see Table 1). *R. biceps* has birotules with extremely slender shaft, which are slightly longer than the diameter of the rotules, and pseudobirotules with a bulbous swelling, bearing dense coarse and blunt spines. *R. pictouensis* has birotules and pseudobirotules smaller in length and diameter than those of *R. montemflumina* sp. nov, but in addition, the oxeas bear stronger spines (see Manconi & Pronzato 2016). The others two

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3 species, are also different to *R. montemflumina* sp. nov. *R. cavernicola* has birotules with
4 large expanded flat rotules deeply cut in a number of long rays. Pseudobirotules in *R.*
5 *cavernicola* have the whole shafts spined or with a set of robust but few spines in the
6 middle, both displaying an extraordinary array of malformations. In *R. sheilae* the rotule of
7 the birotules is expanded and flattened, with slightly to heavily serrated margins, and
8 pseudo umbonated rotules deeply cut into an irregular number of hooks, strongly bent
9 towards the shaft, characteristics that do not occur in *R. montemflumina* sp. nov.
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16 Because sponge classification is based primarily on morphological characters that can
17 display a high degree of phenotypic plasticity, current classifications may not always reflect
18 evolutionary relationships (Hooper & van Soest 2002); thus, the morphological phylogeny
19 is not well resolved, hindered by the paucity of characters available for analysis, and the
20 potential plasticity of these characters. Instead, molecular data have been used more
21 recently to resolve the relationships among sponge taxa (Borchiellini et al. 2000), and it
22 offers much higher resolution and confidence to construct the phylogenetic relationship
23 (Wörheide et al., 2004; Itskovich et al, 2008, Morrow & Cardenas 2015).
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31 Currently, there are not available DNA sequences of the others species of the genus
32 *Racekiella* to compare the phylogenetic position of the new species. However, it was
33 possible to study the phylogenetic relationships of the genus *Racekiella* with the others
34 genus of freshwater sponges using the sequences of *R. montemflumina* sp. nov.
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38 Previous studies on freshwater sponges have shown a low intraspecific variation of *cox1*
39 (see Itskovich, Kaluzhnaya, Ostrovsky, & McCormack, 2013). In fact, they recorded the
40 existence of sequences with an identical nucleotide composition, which involves a variety
41 of species from different families and distant geographical areas (Itskovich et al, 2013).
42 Sequences of *Racekiella montemflumina* sp. nov. were identical to six previous sequenced
43 species, which belong to two families with species recollected in Asia and America. Due to
44 the null information obtained from *cox1*, we prefer not include it in the phylogenetic
45 analysis.
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53 Our phylogenetic reconstruction (based on ITS's rDNA region) was according to
54 previous published topologies, were Lake Baikal representatives (Lubomirskiidae) were
55 grouped in a well-supported monophyletic clade, whereas the monophyly of families
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3 Spongillidae and Malawispongiidae was not resolved (Itskovich et al., 2013; Itskovich,
4 Kaluzhnaya, Veynberg, & Erpenbeck, 2015). As was previously reported, sequences of
5 *Cortispongilla barroisi* (Topsent, 1892) were included in a large clade of representatives of
6 genus *Ephydatia*, suggesting the potential synonymy of the family Malawispongiidae with
7 Spongillidae, although it would be necessary before to study the two remaining
8 Malawispongiidae genera, *Malawispongia* and *Spinospingilla* (Itskovich et al., 2013). The
9 rest of the representative's genera of the family Spongillidae formed monophyletic but in
10 separated clades, which also were previously reported (see Addis & Peterson, 2005;
11 Meixner et al., 2007; Itskovich et al., 2006/2008/2013/2015). Specifically, the genus
12 *Racekiela* (represented by our new species) was clustered separated, between
13 representatives of *Ephydatia* and *Heterorotula* in the principal Spongillidae clade. This
14 position confirms the phylogenetic status of the genus into family Spongillidae, as is
15 suggested by morphological characteristics (see Manconi & Pronzato, 2002). Although it
16 would be interesting include more representatives of the genus in order to establish the
17 internal relationship of group, and corroborate if the morphological characters used in
18 traditional taxonomy are adequate (diagnostic) for species discrimination.
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3 ultrastructure, biocalcification, isotope record, taxonomy, biogeography, phylogeny.
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Table. 1. Spicule micrometries for *Racekiela* spp. All measures in μm .

	Megascleres	Biotules	Rotules	Length birotule/width rotule	Pseudobiotules	Gemmules
<i>R. ryderii</i> (Potts, 1882) ^{1,2}	190-220 x 13-19	30-40 x 3-4	25-27	1.2-1.5	50-75 x 6-8	320-350
<i>R. pictouensis</i> (Potts, 1885b) ¹	165-210 x 17-23	30-40 x 3-4	25-28	1.2-1.4	52-75 x 6-8	350-380
<i>R. biceps</i> (Lindenschmidt, 1950) ¹	260-310 x 15-17	23-26 x 2	20-22	1-1.2	30-42 x 4-5	350-380
<i>R. sheilae</i> (Volkmer-Ribeiro, Barbosa, & Tavares, 1988) ³	259-462 x 4- 17	35-54 x 4-8	26-33	1.3-1.6	41-70 x 2-10	370-543
<i>R. cavernicola</i> (Volkmer-Ribeiro, Bichuette, & De Sousa Machado, 2010) ⁴	359-512 x 10-20	37-58 x 5-11	21-57	1-1.7	60-85 x 6-12	431-483
<i>R. montemflumina</i> sp. nov.	200-325 x 7- 18	47-60 x 5-13	17-23	2.6-2.8	87-105 x 7-13	375-650

¹Penney & Racek, 1968, ²Manconi & Pronzato, 2002, ³Volkmer-Ribeiro, Barbosa, & Tavares, 1988, ⁴Volkmer-Ribeiro, Bichuette, & De Sousa Machado, 2010

Figure captions

Fig. 1. *Racekiela montemflumina* sp. nov. Sampling localities in the state of Durango (yellow marks). Mexiquillo, La Pirámide, Coscomate.

Fig. 2. *Racekiela montemflumina* sp. nov. (2.1) General view of the small creek in Mexiquillo, where the holotype (LEB-ICML-UNAM-4000) was found; (2.2) Close up of a section of the creek where the presence of the sponges is clearly visible from outside (see the white arrows); (2.3) Different rocks covered by large specimens; (2.4) Holotype. Please note the different colour in the specimen; white grey under the rock and green in the area exposed to light.

Fig. 3. La Pirámide sampling area. (3.1) The arrows show the place where the sponge was found; (3.2) One of the paratype (LEB-ICML-UNAM-4002); adhered to an underwater branch; (3.3) A big wooden log completely out of the water, where is clearly visible rest of the specimens (arrows); (3.4) A specimen out of the water totally covered by gemmules.

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of megascleres and spicule malformations. (4.1) Oxeas and detail of the tips; (4.2) Style and detail of its tip and top; (4.3) Different spicule malformations.

Fig. 5. SEM micrographs of gemmuloscleres of the holotype (LEB-ICML-UNAM-4000). (5.1) Birotules and detail of different rotules; (5.2) Birotule with three rotules; (5.3) Pseudobirotules and detail of different pseudorotules.

Fig. 6. LM micrographs of megascleres and gemmuloscleres of the holotype (LEB-ICML-UNAM-4000). (6.1) Oxeas; (6.2) Pseudobirotules; (6.3) Birotules and detail of a rotule; (6.4) Different spicule malformations.

Fig. 7. SEM micrographs of gemmule of the holotype (LEB-ICML-UNAM-4000) ; (7.1) Gemmular surface; (7.2) Gemmular surface with foramen (arrow); (7.3) Detail of the surface of the gemmule where are clearly visible the pseudobirotules rising from the gemmular surface; (7.4) Cross section of a gemmule throughout the foraminal area where are showed the tri-layered theca and the interior plenty of thesocytes; (7.5) Top view of a gemmulosclere birotule; (7.6) Detail of the foramen; (7.7-7.8) Gemmuloscleres multilayered inner layer.

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3 Fig. 8. Tree topology of rDNA region (ITS1-5.8-ITS2) from Order Spongillida, obtained by
4 Bayesian Inference (MrBayes), but also includes Maximum Likelihood (RAxML) values.
5 The number at each node represents the Posterior Probability (%) (BI), followed of the
6 Bootstrap Proportion (ML); a (–) indicates that a particular analysis supported the node at
7 less than 50%, or supported an alternative phylogenetic arrangement in ML tree. The
8 GenBank sequence accession code were included after each species name.
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Fig. 1. *Racekiela montemflumina* sp. nov. Sampling localities in the state of Durango (yellow marks). Mexiquillo, La Pirámide, Coscomate.

202x139mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Fig. 2. *Racekiela montemflumina* sp. nov. (2.1) General view of the small creek in Mexiquillo, where the holotype (LEB-ICML-UNAM-4000) was found; (2.2) Close up of a section of the creek where the presence of the sponges is clearly visible from outside (see the white arrows); (2.3) Different rocks covered by large specimens; (2.4) Holotype. Please note the different colour in the specimen; white grey under the rock and green in the area exposed to light.

199x264mm (150 x 150 DPI)

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184x262mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of megascleres and spicule malformations. (4.1) Oxeas and detail of the tips; (4.2) Style and detail of its tip and top; (4.3) Different spicule malformations.

200x258mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig. 5. SEM micrographs of gemmuloscleres of the holotype (LEB-ICML-UNAM-4000). (5.1) Birotules and detail of different rotules; (5.2) Birotule with three rotules; (5.3) Pseudobirotules and detail of different pseudorotules.

196x268mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig. 6. LM micrographs of megascleres and gemmuloscleres of the holotype (LEB-ICML-UNAM-4000). (6.1) Oxeas; (6.2) Pseudobiotules; (6.3) Biotules and detail of a rotule; (6.4) Different spicule malformations.

200x255mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Fig. 7. SEM micrographs of gemmule of the holotype (LEB-ICML-UNAM-4000) ; (7.1) Gemmular surface; (7.2) Gemmular surface with foramen (arrow); (7.3) Detail of the surface of the gemmule where are clearly visible the pseudobiotules rising from the gemmular surface; (7.4) Cross section of a gemmule throughout the foraminal area where are showed the tri-layered theca and the interior plenty of thesocytes; (7.5) Top view of a gemmulosclere birotule; (7.6) Detail of the foramen; (7.7-7.8) Gemmuloscleres multilayered inner layer.

251x337mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Fig. 8. Tree topology of rDNA region (ITS1-5.8-ITS2) from Order Spongillida, obtained by Bayesian Inference (MrBayes), but also includes Maximum Likelihood (RAxML) values. The number at each node represents the Posterior Probability (%) (BI), followed of the Bootstrap Proportion (ML); a (-) indicates that a particular analysis supported the node at less than 50%, or supported an alternative phylogenetic arrangement in ML tree. The GenBank sequence accession code were included after each species name.

184x202mm (300 x 300 DPI)